

Studies in Acenaphthenequinone Series. Part III.

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In most of the condensation reactions, acenaphthenequinone behaves like phenanthraquinone and yields similar products (*cf.* Sircar and Guha, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 335; Guha, *ibid.*, 1931, 139, 582; Sircar and Guha-Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 93). The present investigation is only an extension of the reactions already studied by one of the present authors.

(A) *o*-Aminophenol and its derivatives (*cf.* Kehrman, *Ber.*, 1905, 33, 2952) condense with acenaphthenequinone forming the ψ -bases acenaphthaphenazoxines. Hydroxy-acenaphtha-5-nitrophenazoxine, obtained by the condensation of acenaphthenequinone with 5-nitro-2-aminophenol, has been obtained in two varieties having identical m.p. (186°) but differing in colour and crystalline shapes. The azoxine, therefore, exhibits chromoisomerism.

The hydroxy-acenaphthaphenazoxines dissolve readily in strong sulphuric acid and on allowing the solution to stand for some time a highly coloured substance separates, which might be either the sulphate or the unstable ψ -base. When the sulphuric acid solution is diluted with water, acenaphthenequinone is precipitated. The phenazoxines when boiled for a few minutes with dilute hydrochloric

acid undergo similar decomposition. It is also interesting to note that the phenazoxines when brominated or reduced with stannous chloride (*cf.* Kehrman, *loc. cit.*), break up regenerating acenaphthenequinone. Evidently the hydroxyacenaphthaphenazoxines are more unstable when compared with the hydroxyphanauthraphenazoxines. In attempting to reduce the phenazoxines by phenylhydrazine according to the method of Kehrman, products are obtained in which the percentage of nitrogen is much greater than that required by the formula of the above author and corresponds with that of the compounds in which one of the oxygen atoms is as if replaced by nitrogen.

(B) Acenaphthenequinone has been condensed with primary amines forming iminazoles and oxazoles (*cf.* Japp and Davidson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1895, 67, 32).

(R = H, Ph, Me)

(R = CH₂Ph, Me, Et; R' = Ph, H, Me respectively).

(C) Acetophenone has been condensed with acenaphthenequinone in presence of acetic anhydride forming 3-acetoxy-2-phenyl-4:5-acenaphthylenefuran (*cf.* Japp and Wood, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 712).

↓ -H₂O

(D) The condensation of acenaphthenequinone with acetic anhydride in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate leads to the formation of two distinct compounds (*cf.* Schwarin, *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 1270) having empirical formulæ $C_{13}H_8O_2$ (green) and C_5H_3O (red). The green compound when heated with potash yields an acid (empirical formula C_5H_3O). The red substance when boiled with potash also yields an acid, identical with the condensation product of acenaphthenequinone with glycollic acid.

(E) Alcoholic caustic potash reacts with acenaphthenequinone (*cf.* Mayer and Spengler, *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 440) forming naphthalic anhydride and the lactone of 8-hydroxyacenaphthyl-7-glyoxylic acid.

In all the studied chemical reactions, therefore, acenaphthenequinone behaves exactly like phenanthraquinone although differing widely from the latter in constitution.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Hydroxy-acenaphthaphenazoxine.—A mixture of acenaphthenequinone (2.5 g.), *o*-aminophenol (1.5 g.) and benzene (50 c.c.) was heated for about 45 minutes, and the solution filtered hot. The deep brown crystals separating were recrystallised from a mixture of benzene and alcohol (1:1) in cubes, m.p. 187° (decomp.). It is sparingly soluble in benzene and water, moderately soluble in nitrobenzene and chloroform. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a deep brown colour (green fluorescence) and on addition of water yellowish brown precipitate is obtained which is identified to be acenaphthenequinone. (Found: N, 5.05. $C_{18}H_{11}O_2N$ requires N, 5.13 per cent).

Attempts to reduce the ψ -base with stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid (*cf.* Kehrman, *loc. cit.*) lead to the decomposition of the ψ -base and acenaphthenequinone is identified as one of the products of decomposition.

Action of Bromine.—The ψ -base (1 g.), dissolved in warm nitrobenzene (10 g.), was treated with a solution of bromine in nitrobenzene (14 g., 10%). After about 10 minutes on the addition of about 5 times the volume of ether, a precipitate separated which after crystallisation from acetic acid was identified to be acenaphthenequinone.

Action of Phenylhydrazine.—The ψ -base was rubbed to a paste with excess of phenylhydrazine and carefully warmed, when a solution was obtained which soon solidified. The solid mass was repeatedly washed with alcohol and repeatedly crystallised from a mixture of benzene and alcohol as orange needles, m. p. 175° . (Found : N, 9.9). The percentage of nitrogen should be exactly half, if the reduction proceeds in the way indicated by Kehrmann (*loc. cit.*).

Hydroxy-acenaphtha-5-nitrophenazoxine.—Acenaphthenequinone (4 g.), 5-nitro-2-aminophenol (3.5 g.) and benzene (150 c.c.) were heated for 2 hours, when a dirty white substance separated. It was filtered and crystallised from alcohol in yellowish orange thick plates, m.p. 186° (decomp.). It is almost insoluble in benzene, but very soluble in alcohol (a deep red colour). (Found : N, 8.43. $C_{18}H_{10}O_4N_2$ requires N, 8.8 per cent). When crystallised from xylene it separates as white needles, m.p. 186° (decomp.). (Found : N, 8.8. $C_{18}H_{10}O_4N_2$ requires N, 8.8 per cent).

The colourless variety dissolves in alcohol to a red solution and on dilution with water the orange variety is obtained. The colourless variety also dissolves in caustic potash solution to a red solution but on acidification the original colourless variety is obtained. The orange variety dissolves in caustic potash and on acidification the colourless variety is obtained.

Action of Bromine and Reduction by Stannous Chloride.—Only acenaphthenequinone has, as in the case of the preceding azoxine, been identified from the reaction mixture after bromination or reduction with stannous chloride.

Action of Phenylhydrazine.—Orange needles (from a mixture of benzene and alcohol), m.p. 161° , were obtained by reacting the above phenazoxine with phenylhydrazine as in the previous case. (Found : N, 14.0 per cent.). The percentage of nitrogen is 50 per cent. above that is required by theory if the reaction goes in the way indicated by Kehrmann (*loc. cit.*).

Acenaphthylene- ψ -phenyloxazole and N-benzylacenaphthylene- μ -phenyliminazole.—An intimate mixture of acenaphthenequinone (2 g.) and freshly fused zinc chloride (1 g.) was added to benzylamine (4 g.) when a brisk effervescence set in. The mixture was then heated to 100° for some time and then at 190° until there was no evolution of ammonia. The reaction product which was obtained as a hard mass

was treated with boiling alcohol and the oxazole was obtained from the alcoholic solution by precipitation with water. The precipitate was dissolved in the least quantity of benzene (charcoal) and petroleum ether added, when a greyish powder was obtained, m.p. 101°. Found : N, 4.6. $C_{19}H_{11}ON$ requires N, 5.2 per cent).

The iminazole was isolated from the alcohol-insoluble portion by crystallising from aniline in yellowish needles, m.p. 260°. It is almost insoluble in common organic solvents, but soluble in concentrated hydrochloric acid. (Found : N, 8.13. $C_{26}H_{18}N_2$ requires N, 7.86 per cent).

Acenaphthylene-oxazole and N-Methylacenaphthylene-iminazole.—Acenaphthenequinone (8 g.) and methylamine (33%, 100 c.c.) were heated in a sealed tube for about 6 hours at 95-100°. As in the previous case the oxazole and iminazole were separated by treating the product with alcohol. The precipitate obtained by adding water to the alcoholic solution, was repeatedly dissolved in hydrochloric acid and precipitated by ammonia. Though very soluble in most of the organic solvents the oxazole could not be crystallised from any one of them and was obtained as a greyish amorphous powder, m.p. 80-82°. (Found : N, 7.2. $C_{13}H_7ON$ requires N, 7.27 per cent).

The iminazole was obtained in minute yellowish needles not melting below 290° by dissolving the alcohol-insoluble portion in aniline and adding benzene drop by drop to the solution. It is insoluble in almost all common organic solvents. (Found : N, 13.12. $C_{14}H_{10}N_2$ requires N, 13.6 per cent).

Acenaphthylene- μ -methyloxazole and N-Ethylacenaphthylene- μ -methyliminazole.—Acenaphthenequinone (10 g.), ethylamine (10 c.c., 33%) and freshly fused zinc chloride (3 g.) were heated in a sealed tube for 8 hours at 160°. The oxazole and iminazole were separated by treating the black reaction product with alcohol. The solution in alcohol was poured into water and the precipitate dissolved in benzene (charcoal) and by adding light petroleum it was obtained as a microcrystalline powder, m.p. 115-17°. (Found : N, 6.65. $C_{14}H_9ON$ requires N, 6.76 per cent).

The portion insoluble in alcohol was washed with acetic acid and hot water. It was finally purified from benzene and obtained as a microcrystalline powder, m.p. above 290°. It is soluble in strong

hydrochloric acid. (Found : N, 11.7. $C_{16}H_{14}N_2$ requires N, 11.96 per cent).

3-Acetoxy-2-phenyl-4:5-acenaphthylene-furfurane.—Acenaphthenequinone (10 g.), acetophenone (14 g.), acetic anhydride (65 g.) and sulphuric acid (d 1.84, 1.5 c.c.) were heated at 50° for 40 hours at 75-80°. The yellow product separating crystallised from benzene as light yellowish green needles, m.p. 257°. It is soluble in acetic acid, benzene and chloroform. (Found : C, 81.2; H, 4.06. $C_{22}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 80.9; H, 4.2 per cent).

Action of Sodium Acetate and Acetic anhydride on Acenaphthenequinone.—Acenaphthenequinone (10 g.), freshly fused sodium acetate (10 g.) and acetic anhydride (60 g.) were heated for 4 hours on the water-bath until there was no quinone left. After keeping overnight the solidified mass was warmed and filtered off from the supernatant liquid. The brownish residue was washed with acetic acid in the cold and then repeatedly with water. The residue crystallised from glacial acetic acid as green nodules (A), not melting below 290°. It is sparingly soluble in acetic acid, insoluble in benzene, alcohol and ether. (Found : C, 80.54; H, 3.03 corresponding to the empirical formula $C_{13}H_8O_2$).

The deeply coloured acetic acid mother liquor was boiled with animal charcoal and diluted with water. The precipitate crystallised from dilute acetic acid in microscopic prisms (B) not melting below 290°. It is soluble in acetic acid and sparingly soluble in benzene and alcohol. (Found: C, 76.40; H, 3.6 corresponding to the empirical formula C_5H_3O).

The green product (A, 1 g.) was heated with a solution of caustic potash 10%, 25 c.c.) for 4 hours. On acidification an orange precipitate separated which when purified from alcohol was obtained as a microcrystalline powder, m.p. 240° (decomp.). (Found: C, 76.60; H, 3.8 corresponding to the empirical formula C_5H_3O).

The red substance (B, 1 g.) was boiled with a solution of caustic potash (10 %, 25 c.c.) and on acidification a yellow product separated which crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 230-31° (decomp.). It is found identical with the lactone of 8-hydroxy-acenaphthylglyoxylic acid (*vide infra*). (Found: C, 75.2; H, 3.1. $C_{14}H_8O_3$ requires C, 75.5; H, 2.7 per cent).

Action of Alcoholic Potash on Acenaphthenequinone.—A mixture of acenaphthenequinone (10 g.) and alcohol (50 c.c.) was heated with

a solution of caustic potash (20 g. in 100 c.c. of alcohol) for 8 hours. The insoluble substance was separated, dissolved in hot water and the solution acidified with hydrochloric acid, when a yellow precipitate was obtained. This was filtered hot and on cooling a white precipitate as obtained, which crystallised from alcohol as colourless needles, m.p. 266°. It is identified to be naphthalic anhydride.

The yellow product (A) crystallised from alcohol as yellow needles, m.p. 230-31° (decomp.) and was identified to be the lactone of 8-hydroxyacenaphthyl-7-glyoxalic acid (*vide infra*). It is soluble in alcohol, benzene and chloroform. (Found: C, 75.78; H, 3.0. $C_{14}H_6O_3$ requires C, 75.5; H, 2.7 per cent).

The Condensation of Glycollic Acid with Acenaphthenequinone.— Finely powdered acenaphthenequinone (5 g.) and glycollic acid (25 g.) were mixed with methyl alcohol (300 c.c.) and then 40 g. of caustic potash added in small bits. It was now heated for 6 hours under reflux. Proceeding as in the case of the previous experiment a yellow crystalline substance, m.p. 230-31° (decomp.) was obtained. It dissolves in sulphuric acid with a blue fluorescence (brown solution).

